

Fabrication of hexagonal-prismatic granular hydrogel sheets

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ABSTRACT

Natural soft materials are often composed of proteins that self-assemble into well-defined structures and display mechanical properties that cannot be matched by manmade materials. These materials are frequently mimicked with hydrogels whose mechanical properties depend on their composition and the type and density of crosslinks. Protocols to tune these parameters are well established and routinely used. The mechanical properties of hydrogels also depend on their structure; this parameter is more difficult to control. In this paper, we present a method to produce hexagonal-prismatic granular hydrogel sheets with well-defined structures and heterogeneous crosslink densities. The hydrogel sheets are made of self-assembled covalently crosslinked 40 - 120 μm diameter hexagonal prismatic hydrogel particles that display a narrow size distribution. The structure and microscale surface roughness of the hydrogels sheets can be tuned with the polymerization conditions, their chemical composition with that of the individual hydrogel particles, and their mechanical properties with the crosslink density. Remarkably, the

hydrogels composed of hexagonal prismatic microparticles are significantly stiffer than unstructured counterparts. These results demonstrate that the stiffness of hydrogels can be tuned by controlling their micrometer-scale structure without altering their composition. Thereby, they open up new possibilities to design soft materials whose performance more closely resembles that of natural ones.

INTRODUCTION

Many natural soft materials have well-defined structures that are vital for their optical¹ and mechanical properties.² For example, the skin of ocellated lizards is composed of close packed hexagonal prisms that allow the lizards to quickly change their appearance.¹ Moreover, the cytoskeleton of cells is made of proteins that self-assemble into filaments and imparts viscoelastic properties to cells that are key for their proper functioning.³⁻⁵ Similarly, the mussel byssus is made of different proteins that are assembled into hierarchical structures, allowing mussels to strongly adhere to solid, hard surfaces.^{6,7} These hierarchical soft materials display a remarkable combination of stiffness and toughness, enabling them to bear loads. For example, the Young's modulus of the mussel byssus of *mytilus edulis* and *Mytilus galloprovincialis* can reach values up to 500 MPa^{8,9} whereas their ultimate tensile stress reaches values up to about 160 MPa.^{8,10} Inspired by the excellent mechanical properties of these natural soft materials, a lot of research is devoted towards designing hydrogels with similar mechanical properties. The mechanical properties of hydrogels can be tuned with the composition, crosslink density, and type of crosslinks.¹¹⁻¹⁴ However, even if hydrogels are covalently crosslinked at a high density, their Young's modulus is at least an order of magnitude lower than that of the mussel byssus and they are significantly more brittle.^{11,14,15} Much tougher hydrogels can be produced, if they contain

ionic crosslinks because these ionic bonds reversibly break, thereby dissipating energy.^{16–19} The relaxation times and hence the viscoelastic behavior of ionically crosslinked hydrogels can be controlled with the choice of the chelator-ion pair^{20–22} or by using appropriate nanoparticles as crosslinking agents.²³ However, the stiffness of these ionically crosslinked hydrogels is much lower than that of mussel byssus. To combine the stiffness of covalently crosslinked hydrogels with the toughness of ionically crosslinked hydrogels, dual network hydrogels that encompass covalent and ionic bonds have been developed.^{24–29} They can be designed to display a combination of stiffness and toughness that has not been achieved by hydrogels only encompassing one type of crosslink. However, manmade dual network hydrogels are still significantly softer than, for example, the mussel byssus.

A major difference between natural hydrogels and manmade dual network hydrogels is their structure. Many natural hydrogels possess hierarchical structures,^{6,30} whereas manmade dual network hydrogels have no defined structure. Controlling the distribution of crosslinks requires fabrication techniques that offer high spatial resolution. Hydrogels are usually formed from solutions containing monomers and an initiator. The shape of hydrogels can be controlled for example using molds^{16,17,28–33} or photomasks.³⁴ More recently, 3D printing methods have been developed that enable production of 3D hydrogels^{35,36} with a spatial resolution down to 5 μm .^{37,38} However, these techniques have never been employed to deliberately introduce granular structures into hydrogels or to control the local crosslink density.

Hydrogels with a heterogeneous distribution of crosslinks can be produced from spherical hydrogel microparticles that are assembled into superstructures.^{39–44} The resulting macroscopic hydrogels have pores whose size is determined by the size and size distribution of the microparticles and their arrangement. To impart mechanical stability to these hydrogels, adjacent

particles must be crosslinked. This can be achieved by covalently crosslinking particles through reactive groups that are presented at their surfaces,⁴⁵ or by adding external crosslinkers.⁴⁶⁻⁵⁰ However, all these microparticles are spherical, limiting the area where adjacent particles are in close proximity and hence, limiting the number of crosslinks between them. As a result, macroscopic hydrogels are fragile and often lose their integrity if removed from the substrate.⁵¹ To improve the mechanical strength, the crosslink-density between adjacent particles must be increased. Feasibility to do so has been shown for spherical microparticles with diameters below $2\ \mu\text{m}$ by functionalizing their surface with additional reactive groups.⁵²⁻⁵⁷ However, the control over the structure and local crosslink density of these particle ensembles was limited because particles were randomly assembled.^{58,59} Hence, fabrication techniques that offer good control over the micrometer-scale structure and local crosslink density of hydrogels remain to be developed.

In this paper, we report the production of macroscopic hydrogel sheets made of regularly arranged, covalently crosslinked $40\text{-}120\ \mu\text{m}$ diameter hexagonal prismatic hydrogel particles that display a narrow size distribution. The structure, local composition, and Young's modulus of these sheets can be tuned with the size and composition of microparticles. Their shape and morphology can be controlled with the polymerization conditions and their Young's modulus with the micrometer-scale structure and the choice of the composition and concentration of monomers they are made from. These results open up new possibilities to tune the structure and mechanical properties of hydrogels that might enable the fabrication of hydrogels whose properties more closely resemble those of hydrogels produced by nature.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Microfluidic device fabrication: Drops are produced in microfluidic millipede devices made of poly(dimethyl siloxane) (PDMS, Sylgard 184, Dow Corning) using soft lithography.⁶⁰ These devices consist of a central channel for the inner phase and on each of the two long sides of the central channel there is a channel for the oil phase. The central channel is connected to the two outer channels through 300 individual drop makers. The nozzle of the drop makers opens in a triangular way, as shown on the optical microscopy image in **Figure S1a**.⁶¹ For a proper functioning of the device, the channel walls must be non-wetting for the inner phases. Therefore, we treat them with an HFE 7500-based solution containing 1% (v/v) trichloro(1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorooctyl)silane (Sigma-Aldrich).

Drop production: An aqueous solution containing 50% (w/w) poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEG700-DA, $M_w \approx 700$ Da, Sigma-Aldrich), a monomer, and 2% (w/w) 2-hydroxy-2-methylpropiophenone (97 %, Sigma-Aldrich), a photoinitiator, is used as the inner phase. To produce fluorescently labeled hydrogels, we add 0.1 mg/mL fluorescein isothiocyanate–dextran (FITC-Dextran, $M_w \approx 150,000$ Da, Sigma-Aldrich) to the aqueous phase containing the monomers and photoinitiator. A perfluorinated oil (Novec HFE 7500, 3M) with 1% (w/w) fluorinated triblock copolymers surfactant, FSH-PEG900-FSH,^{62,63} is used as an outer phase. The two phases are injected into the millipede devices using volume controlled syringe pumps (Cronus Sigma 1000, Labhut, UK). Drops are collected in a glass vial that is wrapped in aluminium foil to protect collected drops from light exposure.

Assembly of structured hydrogel sheets from drops: The density of water is 1.6 times lower than that of the oil such that drops cream inside the collection vial. We remove part of the oil to increase the drop concentration before we deposit this emulsion onto a clean glass slide or into a

25 mm long, 4 mm wide and 120 μm deep PDMS trough. After the drops self-assembled into a monolayer, excessive drops are removed using a micropipette. While the oil evaporates, drops attain a hexagonal prismatic shape. We subsequently illuminate them with UV light ($320\text{ nm} < \lambda < 500\text{ nm}$) that is guided by a liquid light guide with a diameter of 8 mm (Ominicure S 1000, Lumen Dynamics, Canada) for 15 s. The distance between the sample and the end of the light guide is kept constant at 3 cm unless stated otherwise. At this distance, the illumination intensity is 1.20 W/cm^2 , as measured with a radiometer (Suss MicroTec UV optometer). If we vary the distance from 1 cm to 15 cm, the irradiance shifts from 4 W/cm^2 to 0.06 W/cm^2 .

Assembly of structured hydrogels from hydrogel microparticles: To convert drops into hydrogel microparticles, they are illuminated with UV light. The polymerized hydrogel microparticles are washed three times with 2,2,3,3,4,4,4-heptafluoro-1 butanol (TCI) to remove the surfactant and subsequently dispersed into an aqueous solution. We add 20 vol% ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich) to the aqueous dispersion containing the hydrogel microparticles to lower the surface tension, thereby facilitating the spreading of the emulsion on the PDMS substrate; this is required to produce monolayers of microparticles. We deposit a few drops of this dispersion onto a PDMS substrate and let the particles sediment. We subsequently vortex the sample to agitate the particles, thereby facilitating their arrangement into a hexagonal close packed structure.

Interfacial tension measurement: The contact angle between the aqueous solution containing PEG-DA and the substrate as well as the interfacial tension between the PEG-DA solution and the oil is measured using the drop shape analyzer (DSA25, Kruss, Germany).

Microscopy: Samples are visualized with the optical microscope (Eclipse TS 100 and Ti-E, Nikon, Japan). Additionally, some samples are characterized using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, XLF30-FEG, FEI, USA). SEM images are acquired at an acceleration voltage

of 3 kV using a secondary electron detector. To make the samples electrically conductive, they are coated with a 30 nm thick gold film.

Mechanical properties measurement: The Young's modulus of the hydrogel sheets is measured using tensile tests (MiniMat 2000, Rheometric Systems). Samples are dried in air at room temperature for at least 2 days before the measurements are conducted. Sample sheets are immobilized with two clamps that are coated with a 1 mm thick PDMS layer to avoid sample damage. We measure the applied force as a function of the strain and calculate the stress by dividing the force by the cross section of the sample, which we quantify by measuring its width using optical microscopy and its thickness using a digital micrometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To fabricate hydrogel particles with a well-defined size, we employ emulsion drops as templates. Aqueous drops that display a narrow size distribution are produced using a microfluidic millipede device that contains 550 parallelized nozzles, each one having a triangular shape, as shown in Supporting Information **Figure S1a**.⁶¹ We employ a device with 40 μm tall nozzles to produce 119 μm diameter aqueous drops. Their coefficient of variation, defined as the standard deviation of the drop size distribution divided by the mean diameter, is as low as 2.5%, as shown in the optical micrograph in **Figure S1b**.

Two dimensional colloidal crystals composed of hard spheres are usually made by spreading a dispersion containing monodisperse colloids onto a solid substrate and letting the particles arrange into the energetically most favorable crystal structure.^{64,65} To mimic this process, we produce aqueous drops containing poly(ethylene glycol) 700 Da diacrylate (PEG700-DA) and a photoinitiator. These drops are converted into spherical hydrogel particles

through exposure to UV light to initiate the polymerization reaction. The resulting microparticles display a narrow size distribution, as shown in **Figure S1c**. The dispersion is deposited onto a substrate composed of poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) such that the particles sediment. To facilitate the re-arrangement of spherical hydrogel particles into the energetically most favorable hexagonally close packed structure, we agitate the substrate, as shown in **Figure S2a**. However, upon evaporation of the water, the crystal structure becomes defective because the particles shrink without being connected to each other, as shown in the optical micrograph in **Figure S2b**.

To build macroscopic materials from individual microparticles, adjacent particles must be connected to each other, for example by back-filling the structured hydrogels with a second matrix.^{66,67,68} However, this procedure risks infiltration of hydrogel microparticles with the matrix used to back-fill the substrate, such that the structure and properties of the particles are changed. To overcome this limitation, adjacent particles can be connected covalently using reactive groups that are present at their surfaces. This can be achieved if drops rupture before all the monomers are consumed. However, unreacted monomers can only crosslink adjacent particles, if they are located at their surface. Unreacted monomers accumulate at the surface of polymerizing particles, if they are preferentially located at the drop liquid-liquid interface. This is the case if the interfacial tension between the monomers and the oil is below that of the hydrogel particles and the oil.⁶⁹ Here, the interfacial tension between PEG-DA monomers and HFE 7500 is 15.7 ± 0.1 mN/m; it is much lower than that between PEG-based hydrogels that contain a high fraction of water such that we assume this interfacial tension to be similar to that of water/HFE 7500 interfaces, 41.6 ± 0.6 mN/m. Hence, we expect the polymerizing hydrogel particles to be surrounded by monomers that can covalently link adjacent particles.

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration of the formation of hexagonal-prismatic granular hydrogel sheets. Emulsion drops are deposited on a substrate where drops arrange into the energetically most favorable hexagonally close packed structure. Once the majority of the oil is evaporated, drops deform and attain a hexagonal prismatic shape. They are subsequently illuminated with UV light to convert them into hydrogel particles that are linked through their side-walls.

To covalently link adjacent particles, drops must rupture before all the monomers are consumed. The rate at which drops rupture depends on the oil evaporation rate, and thus is in a first approximation independent of the UV light intensity, if we neglect the heating of the UV source. The rate at which monomers are crosslinked depends on the UV light intensity. If we reduce the UV light intensity to sufficiently low values, thereby slowing down the initiation of the polymerization reaction, we expect drops to rupture before all the monomers are consumed. To test this expectation, we deposit drops on a glass slide where they spontaneously assemble into a

Figure 1. a-c) Time-lapse optical micrographs of self-assembled drops taken during the evaporation of the surrounding oil. a) Monodisperse drops self-assemble into a hexagonal close packed structure. b) While the oil evaporates, drops deform and c) attain a hexagonal prismatic shape. d) SEM micrograph of individual hexagonal prismatic particles, obtained by polymerizing the monomers before drops ruptured. e) Top view and f) side view SEM micrographs of granular hydrogel sheets made from drops that were self-assembled on a hydrophilic glass slide.

hexagonally close packed 2D structure and let the oil evaporate, as shown in **Scheme 1**. Once the majority of the oil is evaporated, drops deform to attain a hexagonal prismatic shape, as shown in the time-lapse optical micrographs in **Figure 1a-c**. If they are subsequently illuminated for 15 s with a UV light source that is 1 cm apart from the sample, monomers polymerize before drops rupture such that individual hexagonal prismatic particles result, as shown in the SEM micrograph in **Figure 1d**. By contrast, if we increase the distance between the UV light source and the sample to 3 cm, we can easily detach a connected film composed of the hexagonal

prismatic particles from the glass slide, as shown in **Figure 1e**. However, the particles are not connected through any of their sidewalls. Instead, they are connected through a thin film at the bottom of this structure, as shown in the SEM micrograph in **Figure 1f**. We assign the film formation to the low contact angle between the monomer solution and the glass slide, $14^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$. Hence, the monomer containing aqueous solution wets the glass slide as soon as drops rupture. Upon exposure to UV light, the monomers contained in these thin films polymerize, thereby forming a connecting hydrogel film at the bottom of the particle array. While these structures are mechanically sufficiently stable to be detached from the glass slide, the sheet tends to roll. Rolling is likely caused by the free volume between adjacent hexagonal prismatic particles that is present on one of the sheet sides: This free volume induces contraction of the sheet on one side only and thereby causing a non-uniform deformation that makes its handling cumbersome.

Figure 2. a) Optical micrograph of a hexagonal-prismatic granular hydrogel sheet made by self-assembling drops on a PDMS substrate and subsequently illuminating them with UV light to convert them into hydrogels. The entire sample is shown in the photograph in the inset. b) Top view and c) side view SEM micrographs of granular hydrogel sheet made from hexagonal prismatic particles that are covalently linked to each other. The sample is cut to visualize the connection between adjacent particles.

To connect adjacent particles through their side walls we must avoid the formation of a connecting bottom layer. We expect these connecting films to form because the substrate is wetted by the monomer-containing solution. To test this expectation, we deposit drops onto a hydrophobic substrate made of PDMS; the contact angle between the monomer solution and PDMS is $87^\circ \pm 4^\circ$. After drops attain a hexagonal prismatic shape, we illuminate them with UV light for 15 s. The resulting macroscopic sheets are again mechanically sufficiently stable to be detached from the substrate, as shown in **Figure 2a**. Sheets formed on PDMS substrates remain flat even after they have been detached from the substrate, indicating that the stress distribution along their height is more homogeneous. Indeed, there is no connecting film at the bottom of the particle assembly, as shown in the SEM images in **Figure 2b** and **c**, indicating that adjacent particles are connected through their sidewalls.

To quantify the influence of the granular structure of hydrogel sheets on their mechanical properties, we perform tensile tests on dried samples. The Young's modulus of unstructured

Table 1. Young's modulus of hydrogel sheets as a function of the concentration of monomers contained in drops, their composition, and the hydrogel sheet structure.

Concentration	M _w of PEG	Structure	E (MPa)
50%	700	unstructured	7.7 ± 0.7
		granular	12.0 ± 1.0
	575	unstructured	9.6 ± 1.0
		granular	12.0 ± 1.5
40%	700	unstructured	6.3 ± 0.5
		granular	9.8 ± 0.3
	575	unstructured	6.8 ± 0.8
		granular	9.6 ± 1.2

sheets is 7.7 ± 0.7 MPa, as detailed in **Table 1**, well in agreement with that measured for bulk hydrogels made of PEG-DA with similar molecular weights.⁷⁰ The Young's modulus of hexagonal-prismatic granular hydrogel sheets is significantly higher than that of unstructured counterparts, 12.0 ± 1.0 MPa, as shown in stress-strain curve in **Figure 3a** and summarized **Table 1**. The increased stiffness of granular hydrogels suggests that the average crosslinking density is higher than that in unstructured samples. The density of covalent crosslinks depends on the monomers used to form hydrogels. Hence, the average density of covalent crosslinks

Figure 3. a) Stress vs. strain curves of unstructured (black) and structured, granular (red) PEG700-DA hydrogel sheets. Optical micrographs of the corresponding ruptured sheets are shown in the insets. b) SEM micrograph of the cross-section of a granular hydrogel sheet. The white arrows indicate the voids present in the grain boundaries.

should, in a first approximation, be similar in granular and unstructured hydrogels. The density of physical crosslinks depends on the volume fraction of the polymers. The initial concentration of monomers contained in the aqueous solution is the same for granular and bulk hydrogels. To produce granular hydrogels, this aqueous solution is processed into $120\ \mu\text{m}$ drops that are converted into microparticles through polymerization of the monomers contained in them. If microparticles are produced from spherical drops, they have a diameter of $99\ \mu\text{m}$, resulting in a volume of $5.1 \times 10^5\ \mu\text{m}^3$. By contrast, if particles are produced from drops that are arranged into a hexagonal close-packed structure and deformed into hexagonal prisms, their projected area is $8.9 \times 10^3\ \mu\text{m}^2$ and they are $48\ \mu\text{m}$ tall, such that their volume is $4.3 \times 10^5\ \mu\text{m}^3$. Hence, the volume of these hexagonal prismatic particles is 16% below that of spherical counterparts while the type and number repeat units contained in this volume is the same. These results suggest that the density of physical crosslinks within the hexagonal prismatic particles is higher than that in spherical counterparts. Hence, we also expect it to be higher than that of unstructured

hydrogels that are fabricated without any spatial confinement. This increased density of physical crosslinks within the hydrogel particles is likely a contributing reason for the increased Young's modulus.

Structured sheets rupture along the grain boundaries, as shown in the SEM image in **Figure 2c** and the optical micrograph in the inset of **Figure 3a**, by analogy to the fracture mechanism of ceramics.^{71,72} These results demonstrate that the grain boundaries are the weakest points of the hydrogels. Moreover, these results suggest that the low ductility and toughness observed for the granular hydrogels is related to the grain boundaries. To investigate possible reasons for this reduction in toughness and ductility, we visualize a cross-section of the granular hydrogels using SEM. Grain boundaries encompass long voids, as shown in **Figure 3b**. These voids, which are defects within the granular structure, facilitate crack propagation, thereby lowering the ductility and toughness of the granular hydrogels.

The increase in Young's modulus and the decrease in fracture toughness and ductility caused by the introduction of grain boundaries into hydrogel sheets indicate that the crosslink density inside the particles is high whereas that between adjacent particles is low. We expect this difference in crosslink density to decrease if the density of covalent crosslinks is increased. To test this expectation, we produce particles from PEG-DA with a lower molecular weight, PEG575-DA, which results in a higher density of covalent crosslinks. Also for these samples, the Young's modulus of hexagonal prismatic granular hydrogel sheets is significantly higher than that of unstructured counterparts. However, in agreement with our expectation, the difference in Young's moduli decreases to 25% as summarized in **Table 1**.

Figure 4. a) SEM micrograph of a granular hydrogel sheet composed of spherical particles arranged in a cubic lattice. Drops are assembled using a template containing hexagonal wells that are arranged into a cubic structure. They are polymerized within this template such that their surfaces attain the shape of the wells. b) SEM micrograph of a granular hydrogel sheet composed of hexagonal prismatic particles each one containing semi-spherical dome with a side view of a single particle in the inset. c-e) Optical micrographs of self-assembled drops containing hydrogel particles made by illuminating self-assembled PEG-DA containing drops with a light guide located at a distance of c) 15 cm, d) 10 cm and e) 4 cm from the sample surface.

The density of physical crosslinks depends on the density of polymers and hence on the initial monomer concentration. To test the influence of the physical crosslink density on the mechanical properties, we reduce the monomer concentration to 40 wt%. Indeed, the Young's modulus of these hydrogels is lower and that of granular sheets is again approximately 50% higher than that of unstructured counterparts, as summarized in **Table 1**. If we further reduce the

Figure 5. Fluorescent micrographs of hexagonal-prismatic granular hydrogel sheets composed of a mixture of FITC-dextran labeled and non-labeled particles with a diameter of a) 120 μm , c) 67 μm , and d) 36 μm . b) The normalized fluorescent intensity profile measured along the red line in Figure 5a.

monomer concentration to 30 wt%, the crosslink density between adjacent particles becomes too low such that no integral films can be obtained any more.

Drops spontaneously assemble into the thermodynamically most favorable hexagonal close packed structure, if deposited on a flat substrate, resulting in hexagonal prismatic particles. To test if we can control the drop arrangement and therefore the structure of the resulting granular films, we deposit drops on a PDMS substrate containing 95 μm diameter hexagonal wells. The wells are arranged in a cubic lattice with a distance of 130 μm , which is slightly larger than the drop diameter. After drops are illuminated with UV light, we can detach a connected sheet made of spherical particles that are arranged in a cubic lattice. The bottom surfaces of the

particles have adopted the hexagonal shape of the wells used to arrange the drops into the cubic structure, as shown in the SEM image in **Figure 4a**.

Our results indicate that we can tune the surface morphology of granular hydrogel sheets using templates. However, the use of templates makes the assembly process more time consuming. To test if we can also control the surface topology of these hydrogels without the use of solid templates, we polymerize the hydrogels in two steps: We illuminate the drops with UV light for 3 s immediately after they have been assembled into the hexagonal structure, when they are still spherical. While the majority of the oil evaporates the drops deform into hexagonal prisms. During this process, we observe the formation of domes at the surface of the deformed drops. When all the drops deformed into hexagonal prisms, we expose them again to UV light for 15 s. Thereby, we obtain sheets composed of hexagonal prismatic particles where each particle contains a semi-spherical dome, as shown in the SEM image in **Figure 4b**. The size of the dome can be tuned with the distance between the UV light guide and the sample, as shown in the optical microscopy images in **Figure 4c-e**. These results suggest that a spherical hydrogel particle forms inside the spherical drops when they are illuminated for the first time. As the oil evaporates, drops deform into hexagonal prisms whose height is below the diameter of the growing microparticles such that these particles are trapped in the deformed drops and form domes. The remaining monomers are polymerized when illuminated with UV light for the second time such that hexagonal prismatic particles with semi-spherical domes result. This two-step polymerization enables tuning the micrometer-scale surface roughness of granular hydrogel sheets without the need for any solid template.

The main advantage of using drops to build structured granular hydrogel sheets is the ease with which the crosslink density and composition can be varied locally. To exploit this feature, we produce two different batches of drops with identical sizes but different compositions. We add fluorescein-labeled dextran to one batch of PEG-DA containing drops and produce a second batch of label-free PEG-DA containing drops. The two batches are mixed before drops are assembled on a PDMS substrate and UV illuminated to be converted into granular sheets. The appearance of these sheets closely resembles the skin of cellated lizards, as shown in **Figure 5a**. By analogy to the lizard skin, the composition of these sheets changes over very short length scales, as indicated in **Figure 5b**. The size of the particles can be conveniently varied by controlling the diameter of the drops, as shown in the optical micrograph in **Figure 5c** and **d**.

CONCLUSION

We demonstrate a new method to fabricate hexagonal-prismatic granular hydrogel sheets with locally varying crosslink densities. The sheets are composed of self-assembled hexagonal prismatic particles that are covalently crosslinked through their side walls. The structure, shape, and surface roughness of these sheets can be tuned with the size and arrangement of drops as well as with the polymerization conditions. The mechanical properties of these granular hydrogels can be controlled by tuning their micrometer-scale structure. These granular hydrogel sheets open up new possibilities to design biomimetic soft materials with an increased stiffness that can potentially be used as soft load-bearing structures. This could open up new possibilities to use them for example for tissue engineering or as soft implants. Moreover, it is conceivable to use them as biodegradable replacements for load-bearing polymers that must currently be decomposed or recycled through energy consuming processes.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The Supporting Information containing details on the microfluidic production of water in oil emulsion drops as well as on their conversion into individually dispersed particles is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at x.

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Notes

A patent application for the process to fabricate the granular hydrogels has been filed (GB 1714282.9).

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